

State of the art in privacy preservation in video data

Working Group 2.

Privacy-by-design in audio and video
data

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Details about this white paper

Abstract

Active and Assisted Living (AAL) technologies and services are a possible solution to address the crucial challenges regarding health and social care resulting from demographic changes and current economic conditions. AAL systems aim to improve quality of life and support independent and healthy living of older and frail people. AAL monitoring systems are composed of networks of sensors (worn by the users or embedded in their environment) processing elements and actuators that analyse the environment and its occupants to extract knowledge and to detect events, such as anomalous behaviours, launch alarms to tele-care centres, or support activities of daily living, among others. Therefore, innovation in AAL can address healthcare and social demands while generating economic opportunities.

Recently, there has been far-reaching advancements in the development of video-based devices with improved processing capabilities, heightened quality, wireless data transfer, and increased interoperability with Internet of Things (IoT) devices. Computer vision gives the possibility to monitor an environment and report on visual information, which is commonly the most straightforward and human-like way of describing an event, a person, an object, interactions and actions. Therefore, cameras can offer more intelligent solutions for AAL but they may be considered intrusive by some end users.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) establishes the obligation for technologies to meet the principles of data protection by design and by default. More specifically, Article 25 of the GDPR requires that organizations must "implement appropriate technical and organizational measures [...] which are designed to implement data protection principles [...] , in an effective manner and to integrate the necessary safeguards into [data] processing." Thus, AAL solutions must consider privacy-by-design methodologies in order to protect the fundamental rights of those being monitored.

Different methods have been proposed in the latest years to preserve visual privacy for identity protection. However, in many AAL applications, where mostly only one person would be present (e.g. an older person living alone), user identification might not be an issue; concerns are more related to the disclosure of appearance (e.g. if the person is dressed/naked) and behaviour, what we called bodily privacy. Visual obfuscation techniques, such as image filters, facial de-identification, body abstraction, and gait anonymization, can be employed to protect privacy and agreed upon by the users ensuring they feel comfortable.

Moreover, it is difficult to ensure a high level of security and privacy during the transmission of video data. If data is transmitted over several network domains using different transmission technologies and protocols, and finally processed at a remote location and stored on a server in a data center, it becomes demanding to implement and guarantee the highest level of protection over the entire transmission and storage system and for the whole lifetime of the data. The development of video technologies, increase in data rates and processing speeds, wide use of the Internet and cloud computing as well as

highly efficient video compression methods have made video encryption even more challenging. Consequently, efficient and robust encryption of multimedia data together with using efficient compression methods are important prerequisites in achieving secure and efficient video transmission and storage.

Keywords

Privacy by Design, privacy preservation, visual obfuscation, secure transmission, video data

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1. Cost Action 19121 and this White paper

1.1 Cost Action 19121: GoodBrother

The European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) is a funding organisation for the creation of research networks, called [COST Actions](#) (CA). These networks offer an open space for collaboration among scientists across Europe (and beyond) and thereby give impetus to research advancements and innovation. Many institutions around Europe participate actively in the [CA19121 - Network on Privacy-Aware Audio- and Video-Based Applications for Active and Assisted Living](#), also called GoodBrother.

Europe faces crucial challenges regarding health and social care due to the demographic change and current economic context. [Active and Assisted Living](#) (AAL) technologies are a possible solution to support tackling them. AAL technologies aim at improving the health, quality of life, and wellbeing of older, impaired, and frail people. AAL systems use different sensors to monitor the environment and its dwellers. Cameras and microphones are increasingly used for AAL. They monitor an environment and gather information, being the most straightforward and natural way of describing events, persons, objects, actions, and interactions. Recent advances have given these devices the ability to ‘see’ and ‘hear.’ However, their use can be seen as intrusive by some end-users such as assisted persons and professional and informal caregivers.

GoodBrother aims to increase the awareness of the ethical, legal, and privacy issues associated with audio- and video-based monitoring and to propose privacy-aware working solutions for assisted living by creating an interdisciplinary community of researchers and industrial partners from different fields (computing, engineering, healthcare, law, sociology) and other stakeholders (users, policymakers, public services), stimulating new research and innovation. GoodBrother will offset the “Big Brother” sense of continuous monitoring by increasing user acceptance, exploiting these new solutions, and improving market reach.

1.2 Working Group 2 on Privacy-by-design in audio and video data

This Working Group brings together researchers and industry involved in the design and development of methods to ensure privacy in audio and video data. These include a variety of mechanisms for de-identification of audiovisual data in order to protect privacy while maintaining a certain degree of intelligibility in them, which could be used to recognise events and activities in a supervised (by a carer, non-automated) manner.

This Working Group goals are:

- Review the state-of-the-art of the methods to ensure privacy in audio and video data
- Analyse the capabilities/limitations of the different audio- and video-based devices and current methods to ensure privacy

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- Exchange knowledge in order to obtain more robust methods, which follow privacy-by-default and privacy-by-design principles, for privacy preservation
 - Integrate users privacy preferences in order to design context-aware solutions that are adaptable to different privacy requirements and scenarios
 - Foster the collaboration among participants in research and innovation projects.

1.3 Objectives of this document

The objectives of this document are to:

- Define the role that data protection and privacy has for AAL technologies, providing a short history of privacy by design, from privacy enhancing technologies to data protection by design and by default.
- Present approaches to operationalize data protection by design and by default, from multiple perspectives: legal, engineering, design, stakeholders.
- Review the state of the art of techniques for visual privacy preservation, specially those methods that are more relevant for AAL solutions.
- Review methods for secure transmission and storage of video data.

2. Privacy by design

To understand the role data protection and privacy by design has for Active Assisted Living (AAL) technologies, we provide a short history of privacy by design in this first section. We start by explaining what privacy enhancing technologies (PETs) are and how advancements in this area have created a substantial body of rich literature questioning how privacy goals could be inserted within technology development. Then, after explaining the original ideas from pioneers in the field of privacy, we will explain how such an abstract concept made its way to the law via the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Finally, to close this historical understanding of the underlying and backbone fundamentals of data protection by design, we will describe Art. 25 of the GDPR that codifies the data protection by design and by default.

2.1 Starting Point: Privacy Enhancing Technologies

PETs have been around for a long time, with David Chaum probably as one of the most prominent, early researchers in this field (Chaum, 1985 ; Chaum, 1981; Chaum, Fiat, & Naor, 1988). PETs encompass a broad range of technical means to protect user privacy (Fischer-Hübner, 2009). While various definitions can be found in the literature on what PETs constitute, the European Commission (EC) seems to include within the term PETs every technology that enables compliance with data protection law (EC, Memo/07/159).

Another classification of PETs used by Rubinstein and Good (2020) differentiates between hard and soft PETs. The differentiation is based on how much trust one places on a third party that processes personal data. Hard PETs avoid placing any trust on any third party, which means that the data is minimized to the fullest extent possible, and data sharing is avoided. On the other hand, soft PETs ask how data can be shared with trusted parties only and manage such trusted data sharing practices. The authors argue that PbD - or, more specifically, data protection by design and default as codified within the GDPR - should especially require the implementation of hard PETs (Rubinstein & Good, 2020).

Further classifications of PETs can be found in the literature. Tamò-Larrieux (2018), for instance, clusters different technical means to protect privacy into four clusters: Technical and organizational tools aiming at security, anonymity, autonomy, and transparency. First, security tools align with the technical literature understanding privacy as confidentiality. Here the focus rests on ensuring that data is not disclosed to unauthorized third parties (confidentiality itself), that information remains accurate, complete, unmodified, and consistent (no alteration without authorization; i.e., the integrity of the data), and that information is available and usable by whoever is authorized to do so (availability of the data). Second, anonymity tools enable not being uniquely characterized within a given dataset. Here a distinction - in particular from a legal perspective - must be made between anonymity and pseudonymity. Pseudonymous data under the GDPR is typically still personal data, as one can link two datasets back together. Unlinkability must mean that one cannot distinguish whether two “items of interest” are related or not and are linked to ideals found within the security literature. Likewise, the idea of unobservability, i.e., that one cannot see if an “item of interest” exists is a crucial feature of

anonymity tools. Third, autonomy tools enable individuals to decide for themselves what sort of data processing can occur. Different measures can be used for such an endeavor, e.g., tools regulating access to data (often relying on security tools), blocking unauthorized access, tools regulating permission of data use (who can do what with data), or tools regulating when data is being erased. Fourth, transparency tools provide information on how data is collected, used, and erased. This can occur, for instance, through the provision of information on how the data processing occurs and how data is matched to group profiles.

Table 1. Illustrative examples of PETs

Privacy Enhancing Technologies	
<i>Homomorphic encryption</i> is a newer form of encryption that enables computation over encrypted data. At this stage such processes are still quite computationally heavy and thus expensive.	Security
<i>Secure multiparty computation</i> enables computation of data of groups without revealing who inserted what data. This can be used for instance to determine the average salary among co-workers without sharing to the others nor a trusted party the actual salaries.	Security
<i>Selective disclosure credentials</i> means the authentication of users and proving one is authorized to use a system without revealing further information.	Security / Anonymity
<i>Zero-knowledge proofs</i> allow one to prove to another party that a statement is true without revealing anything else. This can be used for instance for online gambling platforms for the proof to be over 18 but not needing to reveal the exact birthdate or other information.	Anonymity
<i>Differential privacy</i> enables sharing of information about a dataset without actually revealing information about the individual within the data set. The key difficulty is to determine how much noise is added to the dataset for the individual values to remain anonymous before sharing.	Anonymity
<i>Anonymous communication</i> channels hide IP addresses from service providers but allow communication.	Anonymity
<i>Privacy preference settings</i> enable for instance the automatic analysis of privacy policies and setting of preferences (e.g., Platform for Privacy Preferences)	Autonomy
<i>Data sharing tools</i> such as personal data stores or pods enable one to decide what data is shared with certain apps (data locally stored with the user).	Autonomy
<i>Data tags</i> enable to determine access, use, and erasure of data beforehand by tagging the data item. For instance, one can state that one's personal data has to be erased within 30 days after a transaction.	Autonomy
<i>Visualizations provided through dashboards</i> by means of simple icons and simplified text boxes can provide simple and clear insights on how data is being processed.	Transparency

While the above list set up in Table 1 are only some illustrative examples (and by no means a complete list of PETs), we see more and more big tech companies embracing the use of PETs. Apple and Google, for instance, have relied on differential privacy, Google has introduced the FLoC algorithm (standing for:

federated learning of cohorts, with cohorts being users with similar interests) (Bindra, 2021)¹ and Apple is launching privacy labels for services in their app store (Statt, 2020).

Still, even though we see PETs becoming used by these companies, many authors have elaborated on the failures of PETs overall. Famously, Bygrave (2002) stated years ago that PETs are not like household pets, as they are not widely used, not user-friendly, not comprehensible. Likewise, the OECD stated in a 2001 report that the "biggest limitation of PETs is simply lack of consumer awareness" (p. 15). This might also be due to the very different functionalities, capabilities, and user-friendliness of different PETs (OECD, 2001). While this is true, it must be mentioned that not all PETs must be implemented by an individual, but also companies play a role in promoting the use of privacy-friendly technologies. Yet, implementing PETs for businesses comes with a cost (development, implementation, lost opportunities of analyzing data). In this sense, it might also not be surprising that we see larger companies adopting PETs in recent years but not many smaller companies.

2.2 Privacy by Design: Origin and idea

The failures of PETs are partly what motivated the evolution towards the principle of privacy by design. In 1990, Ann Cavoukian, former Information and Privacy Commissioner, came up with the term Privacy by Design (PbD). Her position was that PETs alone were not enough and that there was a clear need for a more holistic approach.

Ann Cavoukian states:

“Privacy by Design is a concept I developed back in the 90’s, to address the ever-growing and systemic effects of Information and Communication Technologies, and of large-scale networked data systems. (...) Privacy by Design extends to a “Trilogy” of encompassing applications: 1) IT systems; 2) accountable business practices; and 3) physical design and networked infrastructure.”

From this quote, we gather that PbD applies not only to the technology or software itself but also to the hardware and infrastructure we build and business practices. Here the educational aspects (i.e., training of staff on privacy) becomes a central issue. Based on this overarching idea, Cavoukian defined seven principles of PbD:

1. **Be proactive and not reactive**, meaning one has to think about privacy before an incident happens, namely during the design phase of a product;

¹ The idea is that the user's browsing data is not shared with Google, but the algorithm locally determines the interest cohort of the user based on that browsing behaviour (only the interest cohort is shared to enable interest-based advertisement. So, the browser calculates via the FLOC algorithm the cohort number; A site demands that number when a user is browsing its site; An ad tech platform then determines what ads to show to the cohort number indicated.

-
2. **Privacy must be the default setting**, because individuals do not deal with privacy settings, the settings must in the most privacy-preserving manner when they start using a service;
 3. **Privacy must be embedded into the design**, meaning the three areas of applications mentioned above (hardware, software, and organizational measures within a company) must be designed in a privacy-friendly manner;
 4. A **full functionality** - positive sum and not zero-sum approach must be followed, meaning that it should be possible to have security and privacy coexist;
 5. **End-to-end security** - full lifecycle protection, targeting the whole lifecycle of data and ensuring it being secure throughout it;
 6. **Visibility and transparency** - keep it open, meaning that components and operation must remain visible to users and providers and that one has the ability to audit what has been promised (trust but verify approach); and
 7. **Respect for user privacy** - keep it user-centric, meaning that the privacy interests of users should be the starting point of any design (this is linked to default mechanisms and transparency requirements (e.g. appropriate notices) and the idea of empowering the user with privacy-friendly options).

2.3 From PbD to Data Protection by Design and Default

It is interesting to see how these principles developed by Ann Cavoukian and the concepts of PETs evolved into legislation. Before elaborating on Art. 25 of the GDPR, which is the first actual codification of PbD ideals into a binding regulation, we would like to shortly highlight important legislative documents that mention PbD or are inspired by PbD.

In 2007, the European Commission released a report (COM(2007) 228 final) to promote and support the development of PETs. The report states: "The use of PETs can help to design information and communication systems and services in a way that minimizes the collection and use of personal data and facilitate compliance with data protection rules." (p. 3) Thus, in that year, we still see a strong focus on PETs within the European Union (EU). The goal was to make PETs more widely used and increase new PETs and implementation. To achieve these goals, the EC proposed various action items, such as standardization, the use of PETs in public authorities, encouraging consumers to use PETs, and raising awareness of consumers.

Second, in 2010 the 32nd International Conference of Data Protection and Privacy Commissioners recognized PbD as an essential component of privacy protection and promoted its adoption (within the so-called Jerusalem resolution that Ann Cavoukian proposed). The resolution on PbD acknowledges challenges for privacy in the digital age and offers PbD as a holistic concept to apply to operations

throughout organizations and design processes. Within the same year, the European Data Protection Supervisor issued an opinion on "Promoting trust in the information society" (2010) and mentioned PbD as a critical tool to promote such trust.

Third, and now on the other side of the Atlantic, in 2012, the FTC issued a report "Protecting Consumer Privacy in an Era of Rapid Change" (2012). The report mentions PbD as a principle in their privacy framework and implementation recommendations. It states: "Companies should promote consumer privacy throughout their organizations and at every stage of the development of their products and services" (p. 22). It urges companies to think about privacy protection and incorporate it into their practices through security measures to ensure reasonable data collection, clear retention and disposal practices, and guarantee data's accuracy. The report also mentioned the need for organizational measures, such as management procedures directed at promoting privacy.

Fourth, in 2012, the OECD issued new Privacy Guidelines (2013). These guidelines acknowledge privacy by design as a new concept that should be implemented (unlike OECD Privacy Guidelines 1980) and mandate the adoption and promotion of technical and educational measures to help protect privacy through national implementation (Part Five: National Implementation).

Fifth, in 2018, to ensure compatibility and coherence with other data protection legal frameworks, particularly with the EU, Convention 108 was updated and modernized and included a mandate on PbD on its protocol. The new modernized version kept the Convention's provisions at the principle level but allowed for a more detailed sectorial text via recommendations or guidelines, reaffirming the Convention's potential for becoming a universal standard for data protection.

Lastly, before elaborating on Art. 25 of the GDPR, it must be noted that its predecessor, the Directive 95/46/EC, already mentioned the use of technical and organizational measures in Art. 17. The article on the security of processing states:

Art. 17 of the Directive 95/46/EC

"Member States shall provide that the controller must implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to protect personal data against accidental or unlawful destruction or accidental loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure or access, in particular where the processing involves the transmission of data over a network, and against all other unlawful forms of processing.

Having regard to the state of the art and the cost of their implementation, such measures shall ensure a level of security appropriate to the risks represented by the processing and the nature of the data to be protected." (Art. 17(1) Directive 95/46/EC).

The article must be read in conjunction with the Rec. 46 of the Directive 95/46/EC:

Rec. 46 of the Directive 95/46/EC

“Whereas the protection of the rights and freedoms of data subjects with regard to the processing of personal data requires that appropriate technical and organizational measures be taken, both at the time of the design of the processing system and at the time of the processing itself, particularly in order to maintain security and thereby to prevent any unauthorized processing; whereas it is incumbent on the Member States to ensure that controllers comply with these measures; whereas these measures must ensure an appropriate level of security, taking into account the state of the art and the costs of their implementation in relation to the risks inherent in the processing and the nature of the data to be protected;” (Rec. 46 Directive 95/46/EC)

What stands out is that the focus rests on security, which, as mentioned above, is only one aspect of PETs and PbD. Nonetheless, early on, the focus rested on the whole life cycle of data, an approach that also today is valid.

Art. 25 of the GDPR

Art. 25 of the GDPR codifies the ideals of PbD into a new norm called Data Protection by Design and Default (DPbDD). To distinguish between the two, we will consistently use PbD when referring to the broader ideals proposed by Ann Cavoukian and to DPbDD when talking about Art. 25 of the GDPR.

Art. 25 of the GDPR reads as follows:

Art. 25 of the GDPR

“1. Taking into account the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons posed by the processing, the controller shall, both at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of the processing itself, implement appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, which are designed to implement data-protection principles, such as data minimisation, in an effective manner and to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation and protect the rights of data subjects.

2. The controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures for ensuring that, by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed. That obligation applies to the amount of personal data collected, the extent of their processing, the period of their storage and their accessibility. In particular, such measures shall ensure

that by default personal data are not made accessible without the individual's intervention to an indefinite number of natural persons." (Art. 25(1) and (2) GDPR)"

The GDPR codified into law and laid down the all-encompassing design principles for better privacy and security of products and services in the EU on its art. 25. Although the idea that privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) could restore the balance between data processing entities and data subjects has been around for a while, these technologies are not very popular. Still, valuable literature emerged within the field of privacy engineering due to these advancements, and novel proposals within this field of data protection encoding law have emerged.

The PbD principle enshrined within the GDPR may not be as ambitious as the original PbD principles coined by Cavoukian. Still, it fundamentally aims to implement all the principles of data protection law through technical and organizational measures throughout the whole life cycle of data and focus on security issues and overall adherence to the principles of processing (Tamò-Larrieux, 2018; Bygrave, 2020). Moreover, Article 25 focuses "more strongly on the data subjects and their rights to technical protection measures, rather than leaving the implementation to the discretion of the data controller. The latter is called upon to ensure that certain privacy protection features are used by default." (Tamò-Larrieux et al., 2021).

Article 25 GDPR targets data controllers mainly, who are responsible for implementing measures by design and by default. While this interpretation does not consider that a third party often designs technical infrastructures, it imposes the duty to comply with the norm to the data controller as soon as the controller determines the means and purposes of processing (Bygrave, 2020). The lack of widening of the norm addressee has been criticized in the literature, as it undermines "the goal of ensuring the privacy interest are fully integrated into information system architectures" (Bygrave, 2020, p. 578). Still, the data flows' contextual dimensions and the resulting informational privacy issues thereof would challenge software companies' success in ensuring that all their products adhere to the fundamental principles of data protection by design and default. Such an interpretation would require a more privacy engineering and technically holistic approach to PbD, which would mandate a broader implementation of available privacy-enhancing technologies by developers (Rubinstein & Good, 2020). Until now, still, it remains the data controllers' responsibility to mandate developers within their entity and contracted third parties to ensure that principles concerning the legality of the data processing (e.g., transparency, lawfulness, purpose limitation, information requirements), principles concerning the design of the data processing (e.g., data minimization and proportionality, disclosure and storage limitation, security, data quality), principles concerning individual rights (e.g., participation principle, accessibility, enabling erasure and object to the processing), as well as principles concerning the compliance and enforcement (e.g., accountability, documentation) are implemented by appropriate technical and organizational measures (Tamò-Larrieux, 2018).

2.4 Implementing Data Protection by Design and by Default

Because Implementing DPbDD is not an easy task (Koops & Leenes, 2014; Schartum, 2016; Garcia et al., 2021), what remains somehow unclear is what DPbDD means in practice and how the Art. 25 of the GDPR can be operationalized. EU data protection law accommodates different regimes combining overarching principles with justificatory legal grounds, and it is usually written very vaguely. This duality demands data controllers to prove compliance with pre-determined grounds and enables them within a set of boundaries to determine how to implement data protection's broadly defined principles (Tamò-Larrieux, Mayer, & Zihlmann, 2020).

2.4.1 Legal perspective

Art. 25 of the GDPR sets out in the first sentence with a *balancing approach* by requiring data controllers to consider the state of the art technologies, the cost of implementation of such technologies, the context and circumstances of the data processing, as well as the risk associated with the data processing. These aspects are rather broad and leave much leeway to data controllers to determine adequate measures in a particular context. However, specific guidance on how to determine what measures are adequate in certain circumstances has been issued. For instance, ENISA issued a report on what the “state of the art” refers to, arguing that only technologies that have reached a certain maturity level must be considered (ENISA, 2015).

ENISA also released guidance and an online tool² to determine risks by conducting data protection impact assessments (DPIA) on the belief that the assessment of risks is the first step towards adopting appropriate security measures for the protection of personal data. In this respect, the GDPR establishes specific criteria to assess a high-risk situation: for instance, automated decision making is involved, systematic monitoring, sensitive data, vulnerable data subjects, large scale, new technological solutions. In these situations, one has to conduct a DPIA and show mitigating measures.

This guidance is helpful to determine what measures to implement. Moreover, the recitals of the GDPR also provide further details on what policymakers had in mind. For instance, Rec. 78 states:

Recital 78 of the GDPR

The protection of the rights and freedoms of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data require that appropriate technical and organisational measures be taken to ensure that the requirements of this Regulation are met. In order to be able to demonstrate compliance with this Regulation, the controller should adopt internal policies and implement measures which meet in particular the principles of data protection by design and data protection by default. Such measures could consist, inter alia, of minimising the processing of personal data, pseudonymising personal data as soon as possible, transparency with regard to the functions and processing of personal data,

² See <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/risk-level-tool> (accessed on 02/03/2022).

enabling the data subject to monitor the data processing, enabling the controller to create and improve security features. When developing, designing, selecting and using applications, services and products that are based on the processing of personal data or process personal data to fulfil their task, producers of the products, services and applications should be encouraged to take into account the right to data protection when developing and designing such products, services and applications and, with due regard to the state of the art, to make sure that controllers and processors are able to fulfil their data protection obligations. The principles of data protection by design and by default should also be taken into consideration in the context of public tenders.

In addition, because of the fines provided if DPbDD are not implemented (according to Art. 83 GDPR up to 10 million Euros or 2% of the annual turnover), we expect to see more decisions of data protection authorities or even courts on the issue. At the moment, according to the GDPR enforcement tracker³, around 30 decisions mentioning Art. 25 of the GDPR can be found. One prominent case was issued by the data protection authority of Berlin to a real estate company for not deleting unnecessary old data within their internal system and not determining beforehand what data was necessary to be kept (EDPB, 2019).

As a starting point, methodologies for reliably embodying values like privacy and data protection into AAL systems need to be developed. One approach for how privacy can be operationalized and implemented in the development of AAL technologies starts with conducting a contextual understanding of privacy, particularly privacy threats or risks posed by the technology (Mihailidis and Colonna, 2020). Here, theoretical and empirical studies conducted by experts in human-computer relations are necessary. Next, an analysis of the relevant black-letter law and a systematic approach as to how to incorporate the requisite legal rules into AAL solutions follows. In this methodology, it is key to consider the specific design elements of these kinds of systems which include: sensors, the models, the system, the user interface, and the user, discussed in more detail below. DPbD techniques should be implemented in order to meet legal requirements.

At the **sensor level**, privacy preservation techniques may prevent the capture of sensitive data in visual feeds using various software and hardware implements. These mechanisms can prevent the capture of sensitive content in the first place by the camera. This can also be implemented at the software level, as a filter to clear the captured images of protected content before the images are stored to disk.

At the **model level**, methods are created that preserve privacy for users while at the same time enabling models to infer information from data. Privacy-preserving data mining (PPDM) is emerging as an

³ See <https://www.enforcementtracker.com/> (accessed on 02/03/2022).

important set of techniques that can be used to maximize the benefits of large datasets while, at the same time, minimize the privacy impacts.

For **system level** privacy preservation, it is required that the data used in the pipeline becomes secure, and that user consent for the use of the data in the pipeline is traceable. Traceability requires two components. The first is that personal data can be traced to when user consent for its use was recorded. Secondly, the flow of the data to various sources should also be traceable. This is essential because withdrawal of consent is an important facet of privacy laws like the GDPR; upon withdrawal of consent, actions have to be taken by the authorized administrator to comply with the request.

At the **user-interface level**, the functionality of an AAL application should be adjusted to the competence of the user in order to increase the transparency of data processing and to strengthen data privacy. ENISA suggests that privacy-friendly default configurations and settings, intelligible to this population should be used (ENISA, 2011).

User level privacy measures empower users by helping them manage their data. These also help users understand the privacy risks involved with the sharing of their data, and also give them mechanisms with which they can control the disclosure of their data.

2.4.2 Engineering perspective

In this section, we briefly outline selected engineering approaches to Privacy by Design in general. In the following Sections, we review in detail the existing privacy preservation techniques in video (Section 3) as well as unpack the secure transmission mechanisms for these types of data, specifically in the context of Active and Assisted Living (Section 4).

System engineering researchers experimented with numerous tools and techniques to handle privacy preferences in complex software enterprise systems and social media sites and conceived workable privacy solutions to manage access to sensitive data in the context of work and personal computing. These engineering approaches assume that privacy is pre-defined and can often be manifested as “control over personal data through notice and choice” (Wong and Mulligan, 2019).

The research focused on usable privacy in software systems has explored how personal data protection can be implemented within the framework of PbD and DPbDD, as both are not concrete enough to ensure data protection principles at the (implementation) level of information systems (Gürses et al., 2011). In turn, privacy design strategies and privacy patterns provide more explicit engineering recommendations, which software engineers can adopt. Furthermore, privacy enhancing technologies are yet another example of how personal data protection may be implemented in specific contexts (Danezis et al., 2014).

Hoepman (2014) proposed eight privacy design strategies, bridging legal and technical requirements for personal data protection. These include *minimize, separate, abstract, hide, inform, control, enforce, and demonstrate*. These high-level strategies can be seen as architectural goals in software systems design.

In addition to that, Hoepman offered complimentary tactics on how to achieve these goals. The usable privacy research community adopted his strategies and tactics to organize, categorize and develop more concrete engineering suggestions and privacy patterns.

Privacy researchers created collections of bite-size design patterns (e.g., <https://privacypatterns.org> and <https://privacypatterns.eu>) for software developers to guide them in effectively communicating to end-users how their personal data is used in a given information system. The privacy patterns from these collections provide well-described solutions to recurrent problems in the area, outline their context of use, possible implications, and consequences for systems design, and offer an example from an existing system.

Furthermore, Colesky and Caiza (2018) proposed a pattern system consisting of 31 interconnected privacy patterns that “helps inform software developers so that they can inform their users” about their personal data handling. Their pattern system utilizes Hoepman’s *inform* privacy strategy and associated tactics (i.e., *notify*, *provide*, and *explain*) to organize and filter privacy patterns from the aforementioned collections. They argue that through examining interactions among patterns, patterns systems can promote easy identification of the right pattern for a given context and highlight the pattern’s significance in the collection, which, in turn, can reduce the complexity of information systems and enhance their efficiency and extensibility (Gamma et al., 1994).

Extending the issues of data protection beyond systems engineering efforts, we briefly outline the emergent challenges of the use of personal data for the purposes of research. Recently, the amount of the study participants’ confidential and sensitive data made available to researchers has seen a dramatic increase. The key challenge for researchers dealing with such data and those managing access to the data is to avoid any residual disclosure risks (Ritchie and Elliot, 2015). Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) (Ritchie and Elliot, 2015) is an example of a technique for how these risks can be mitigated. SDC seeks to transform data in such a way that they can be publicly released whilst preserving data utility and statistical confidentiality, where the latter means avoiding disclosure of information that can be linked to a specific individual or corporate respondent entities.

Micro-aggregation (e.g., Domingo-Ferrer and Mateo-Sanz, 2002) is a popular SDC technique consisting in the aggregation of individual data. It can be considered as an SDC sub-discipline devoted to the protection of individual data, also called micro-data. Micro-aggregation can be seen as a clustering problem with constraints on the size of the clusters. It is somehow related to other clustering problems (e.g., dimension reduction or minimum squares design of clusters). However, the main difference of the micro-aggregation problem is that it does not consider the number of clusters to generate or the number of dimensions to reduce, but only the minimum number of elements that are grouped in the same cluster.

Ritchie and Elliot (2015) offered a taxonomy for SDC. They differentiated traditional rule-based models for data access from emergent principle-based approaches, which are deemed more secure and cost-

effective albeit requiring greater initial investments. They reviewed arguments for the two approaches and concluded that the principle-based approach *“is generally preferable, and it is essential for the remote research data centres which dominate access solutions for the most sensitive data.”* When designing systems with privacy in mind, a principle-based approach can be exercised through the disclosure control based on mathematically-driven approaches to PbD such as *differential privacy* (see Dwork, 2008 for a survey of techniques to achieve this). We further outline the other computationally-laden approaches in Section 3.

2.4.3 Design perspective

In this section, we briefly outline recent work, which exemplifies contemporary design efforts in the context of PbD. Wong and Mulligan (2019) conducted a comprehensive systematic literature review of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) scholarship on privacy and design and discussed the specific contribution of design in PbD research. They offered a set of dimensions along which design relates to privacy: (a) the multifaceted purpose of design in privacy work; (b) the actors involved in doing design; and (c) the envisioned beneficiaries for whom design work is meant to serve. They mapped various design orientations and methodologies (e.g., Software Engineering, User- and Value-Centered Design, Re-appropriation, and Speculative Design) to the main purposes of approaching privacy (e.g., solving a specific problem, exploring people requirements in different contexts, informing and supporting end-users choices, and providing critique). Furthermore, they reflected on the role of design authorities and involved stakeholders unpacking different configurations of *who* is doing design work and *for whom* this work is expected to benefit. Based on this mapping, the authors proposed new roles that HCI and design can play in PbD to foreground emergent social values and help identify and scope new privacy problem spaces *“by taking up participatory, value centered, and speculative and critical design practices as part of PBD’s repertoire”* (Wong and Mulligan, 2019).

Yao et al. (2019) conducted a co-design study to explore user-centered privacy designs for smart homes. Instead of designing privacy tools only by experts, the authors engaged various groups of participants with diverse backgrounds and levels of experiences with smart homes to explore how people desire to protect their privacy in the domestic context. That can be further translated to practice to aid the wide adoption of smart home solutions – a market, where privacy (with its associated concerns of continuous data collection, sharing, and misuse) has been identified as the main roadblock (Jacobsson and Davidsson, 2015; Kumar et al., 2016). They distinguished six key design factors for privacy mechanisms for smart homes: (1) data transparency and control; (2) security; (3) safety; (4) usability and user experience; (5) system intelligence; and (6) system modality. By discussing the intricacies of privacy in the context of home, in particular: information privacy vs. physical privacy, and the complexity of power dynamics and social relationships, which may lead to varying privacy norms; the authors posed an open-ended question for designers of smart home privacy mechanisms: *“Whose privacy should be protected and who should make the decision?”*

Driven by the convoluted legal rules and incumbent privacy regulations when it comes to personal data protection, Luger et al. (2015) created and field-tested a privacy-focused design toolkit to be employed

at the early stages of a design process (i.e., ideation) to highlight emergent European data protection issues and associated hindrances in the design of interactive systems, which need to process and store personal user data. The toolkit, a collection of GDPR-inspired cards, is geared toward design practitioners and researchers to conceptualize operationalizable heuristics and development guidelines, which can be used in system design therefor. During deployment of the toolkit with the several groups of design practitioners they concluded that despite an emergent call for accountability in design, the (data protection) regulation is merely viewed as a compliance issue. They concluded that, while wishing to protect users, designers struggle to engage with regulations. The authors, ultimately, called for the development of translational resources (Colusso et al., 2017) to draw designers into the co-production of meaningful privacy heuristics by implementing human-centered design approaches to regulation.

Collectively, the role of design and design practices are less explored in the contemporary privacy discourse in the PbD research. A small number of prior studies looked at situating design scholarship in the PbD context, developed specific methods (e.g., based on participatory and co-design approaches) and taxonomies to involve various stakeholders in a privacy-inclusive design process, as well conceptualized a set of design instruments (e.g., toolkits and patterns) to aid transfer knowledge between design research and design practice. At the same time, user and stakeholders' perspectives to manage convoluted privacy requirements online became a so-called “wicked problem” (Rittel and Webber, 1973) – a problem that is hard to conceptualize and approach due to the often contrasted views of the involved parties. Therefore, in what follows next we decided to include a stakeholder engagement and retainment perspective to emphasize the need for continuity to establish and review privacy requirements of interactive systems and platform-based digital services across different target audiences and over time.

2.4.4 Stakeholders (Engagement) perspective

In this Section, we briefly review the stakeholder engagement perspective on PbD through inclusive and user-centered design approaches. The British Standards Institute (BSI, 2005) defines inclusive design as: ‘The design of mainstream products and/or services that are accessible to, and usable by, as many people as reasonably possible [...] without the need for special adaptation or specialised design.’ Inclusive design means that most products cannot be designed to address the needs of the entire population, but can be used broadly if guided by an appropriate design response to diversity.

One successful method to improve stakeholders' privacy is through user-centered design (UCD), an iterative design process in which designers focus on the users and their needs in each phase of the design process. With close user involvement, products are more likely to meet their expectations and thus be more successful in the market, safer, ethical (namely respecting privacy and quality of life) and more sustainable.

In general, UCD consists of four phases: (1) needfinding; (2) design; (3) prototyping; and (4) evaluation. The process is often iterative, it starts from understanding the context of use, to specifying the user needs, wishes and requirements, to designing alternatives for an envisioned requirements. A design

phase follows the development of solutions, which leads to their evaluation. From here, further iterations of these four phases may occur until the evaluation results are satisfactory. A stakeholder evaluation report can be generated at the end of each iteration and be available at later stages for developers to build on.

Privacy is one area where the user-centered design methods could be wisely applied, as they directly concern the user as the data owner (data-subject). A framework that enables developers and designers to grasp privacy through a user-centered approach, that is used iteratively and implemented along the software development life cycle may bring usability and adoption gains that are not to be discarded.

Senarath et al. (2017) propose an Approach for User-Centric Privacy following the steps illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. User-centric privacy framework (reprinted from (Senarath et al., 2017))

Privacy expectations, responsibility and potential vulnerabilities of all stakeholders involved in a system should be duly considered if we aim to achieve effective privacy. In this concept of stakeholders, not only the end-users of the system are included but any actor involved in the conception, deployment, use or upscale and their requirements, perceptions and behaviors with the system are useful to be perceived.

This understanding can directly impact the decision of the developers regarding data minimisation and other privacy parameters such as accountability, a strong criterion in effective privacy implementation that ensures reliable and responsible systems (Cavoukian et al., 2010).

Within this scope, it is relevant to refer to a set of 31 privacy preference terms developed within the framework of the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing (EIP-AHA), the EIP-

AHA Privacy Preference Terms, assembled by a working group from various sources and based on 15 specific use cases (Zimmermann and Dantas, 2018). Each EIP-AHA Privacy Preference Term addresses a specific privacy setting that occurs in one or multiple use cases. They are structured along categories and sub-categories and include a section dedicated to video and one other for audio, each including several sub-categories.

In determining a user's preferred collection of privacy settings, a system using these would ask the user some relevant "privacy setup questions", or let the user choose between a set of pre-defined privacy settings (e.g. represented as personas) - or both for different areas. The privacy preferences shall then work across all AHA solutions of the user. This structure acknowledges that "one size fits all" does not work for privacy settings for individual users; they must have full control to define their preferences and/or be supported by their caregivers or family members in this scope, if necessary, thus being more empowered to understand the "costs and benefits" of data sharing.

The EIP-AHA Privacy Preferences do not intend to replace or overlap but be complementary to data protection laws, being useful as a tool to collect the user's will on how their data are processed across application and platform borders. This means that a user's personal privacy settings may further restrict a system's data processing capabilities, even beyond what data protection laws would allow. On the other side, data protection laws must always be observed, disregarding a user's personal preferences on privacy.

3. Privacy preservation in video

There are two major reasons attributed to why visual privacy ought to be preserved. The first is identity protection, where a person's identity needs to be hidden from entities analysing visuals without permission. These entities, commonly referred to as adversaries in literature, can either be machine learning models training and inferring on user data without consent, or humans who view visual feeds without obtaining the necessary consent for access. However, in some AAL solutions, where mostly only one person would be present (e.g. an older person living alone), user identification might not be an issue; concerns are more related to the disclosure of appearance (e.g. if the person is dressed/naked) and behaviour, what we called bodily privacy. A level of trust needs to be preserved in these scenarios, where cameras might be deployed in privacy-sensitive areas around the house like bedrooms and bathrooms. Here, the identity of the person is of less importance, considering that consent has already been provided by the monitored person. This survey considers this latter scenario to be of more relevance for this Section, and the methods surveyed in greater detail are those which provide bodily privacy.

To preserve privacy in such scenarios, it is often the case that multi-stage pipelines are employed. To preserve trust, it is necessary for privacy to be preserved for the end user at every stage of such a pipeline, and information of importance is provided to the end-user to gauge how and where their data is being used by the system. PbD is a framework that aims to ensure privacy in this manner. Therefore, this idea is explored in more detail in this Section, and connections between high-level system design concepts relating to privacy by design and low-level concepts in computer vision relating to visual privacy protection methods is also put forward. This is to show that various methods that are proposed in the literature to provide visual privacy contribute to different levels while designing a system that ensures privacy by design.

3.1 Visual privacy protection methods

Visual privacy protection methods can be classified under 5 major categories (Figure 2). These categories, built upon the taxonomy developed by Padilla Lopez et al. (2015), are as follows:

- **Intervention methods** - These interfere during data collection, limiting the amount of private visual information that can be collected from the environment. These methods physically intervene camera devices to prevent the acquisition of an image by means of a specialised device that interferes with the camera sensor. Intervention methods can be classified into sensor saturation, broadcasting commands, and context-based approaches (Pérez et al., 2017). **Sensor saturation** provides privacy by feeding the acquisition sensor with a saturating signal greater than the maximum input the sensor supports. This can be obtained by physical intervention, for instance stickers or webcam covers usually employed in laptops. Other methods locate retro-reflective CCD or CMOS in the vicinity and directs pulsing lights to distort the recorded images. Some devices are able to **broadcast commands** to disable input

Figure 2. A taxonomy of visual privacy preservation techniques for AAL

devices in the surroundings. For instance, a camera with inbuilt facial recognition might blur sensitive areas after receiving specific commands (Pilu, 2007). In **context-based approaches**, the input sensor is intervened based on context recognition, for instance, a specific location (Kapadia et al., 2007).

- **Blind Vision** - These are algorithms that rely on secure multiparty computation (SMC) techniques from cryptography and which allow computer vision tasks to be executed without compromising on the privacy of the data used for computation, nor of the algorithm itself.
- **Secure Processing** - These are algorithms that allow processing private data in a unidirectional manner. This implies that the database queried would be a public one, but the query and its results are kept private. Secure processing algorithms do not rely on SMC techniques.
- **Data Hiding** - These are reversible privacy preserving algorithms where the information required for reversal to the original is stored in the original image itself, using techniques such as steganography, digital watermarking, and fingerprinting.

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- **Visual Obfuscation** - Other methods that hide sensitive visual information from adversaries of various sorts are termed visual obfuscation techniques. This techniques are detailed in Section 3.2.

3.2 Visual obfuscation techniques

Visual obfuscation to be the most important of the above-mentioned categories because of its particular relevance to bodily privacy. Visual obfuscation methods can be further split into two categories based on the adversary from whom the information in the visual is to be obfuscated. These are *perceptual obfuscation* and *machine obfuscation* methods.

3.2.1 Perceptual obfuscation

Perceptual obfuscation methods impart visual privacy through creating visuals in which the privacy-sensitive elements are perceptually different from the original. The simplest methods in this category are arguably blurring and pixelation, two methods that are widely used in media for obscuring privacy-sensitive elements in visuals. Although the lines are blurred, perceptual obfuscation techniques can broadly be split into five subcategories - *Image filtering*, *total body abstraction*, *gait replacement*, *facial obfuscation*, and *environment replacement*.

Perceptual obfuscation methods can either be reversible in nature, where the original image can be retrieved after modification, or be irreversible. Much of the classical literature in perceptual obfuscation has been reviewed in Padilla-López et al. (2015). The following subsections deal with the state-of-the-art in each of the major subcategories of perceptual obfuscation methods.

Image filters

In broad terms, image filtering relies on the alteration of image pixels in various ways that imparts privacy to an image. Image filters can be applied globally to entire images, or to sensitive parts of images where privacy is required (Figure 3). The simplest forms of filters are *blurring*, *pixelation* and *warping*.

Blurring filters apply a Gaussian function over an image. This function modifies each pixel of an image using neighbouring pixels. As a result, a blurred image has a reduced resolution in the areas in which the filter has been applied. Although widely used in applications as large as Google Maps, blurring has been shown to be ineffective against various recognition software even when being de-identified to human observers. A pixelating filter divides an image into a grid. For each block in the grid, an average colour over all the pixels within the block is calculated and assigned to each pixel within the block. Pixelation has been widely used in the media, especially to obscure the identity of subjects who want to remain anonymous. In warping, a set of keypoint parameters are determined using face detection techniques. These keypoints are then shifted according to a 'warping strength' parameter. The new intensity values are determined using interpolation.

Figure 3. Result of the application of different filters to an image from the Toyota Smarthome dataset: (from left to right) original, pixelated, blurred, replacement with an avatar (adapted from (Climent-Pérez and Florez-Revuelta, 2021))

These simple techniques have, however, been shown in various studies to not be robust in providing privacy (Newton et al., 2005; Korshunov and Ooi, 2011). Newer, more advanced forms of filtering techniques have also been developed. Çiftçi et al. (2015) devise false colours as a filter to impart visual privacy to images. For this method, RGB images are first converted into greyscale. A number of colour palettes are devised for this step, and depending on the colour palette chosen, the pixel intensity is mapped into a pre-defined set of RGB pixel values. This creates filtered images. This false colour filter scheme also allows for reversible transformations from which the original image can be retrieved, through the storage of a difference image and a sign image. Being a fairly generic method, the false colour scheme can be applied to nearly any RGB image, regardless of pre-processing already done on the image.

Adaptive blurring (Zhang et al., 2021) is an algorithm that relies on semantic segmentation masks to guide the process of blurring on the video. The model relies on two steps. First, the authors use a deep neural network, DeepLab (Chen et al., 2017), to segment the privacy-sensitive parts of the visual feed. Then, a scale-dependent Gaussian blur is devised for blurring those parts defined by the mask. A custom strategy based on symmetry is created to guide the application of the Gaussian blur on the edges of the objects in question. The scheme and its results can be seen in Figure 3. An issue with this method is that the algorithm might miscalculate the amount of blurring necessary to conceal specific objects or parts of an image.

Cartooning is another technique that has been proposed for filtering images. For instance, Hassan et al. (2017) locate privacy-sensitive objects in an image, replacing them with appropriate clip art.

PECAM, devised by Wu et al. (2021) is a system that allows for data hiding-based reversible image transformations. The system is built for streaming and allows for the creation of filtered images that can then be reconstructed if such a need arises. In this scheme, depending on whether the model aims to reconstruct the images after transformation, different directions in the pipeline are followed. A generator neural network (referred to as a *transformer* in the paper) and a discriminator network (termed as *reconstructors*) are trained using a cycle consistent GAN approach (Zhu et al., 2017). The transformer is used to generate filtered images, and the reconstructor is used to reverse the transformation if need be.

In the pipeline that facilitates reconstruction, a secret key is generated, which is subsequently used by the transformer and the reconstructor to guide the transformations. This is embedded into the image using data hiding as an alpha channel. These RGBA images are then fed to the generator network which, post compression, produces filtered images that preserve privacy, which can then be broadcast to viewers. Filtered images can also be fed to the reconstructor to create a reconstruction of the original image using the alpha channel. In cases where reconstruction is not necessary, a lightweight network is used as the generator, which is created through model distillation techniques (Ba and Caruana, 2013), using the original network as a teacher. Post-compression, the output of this student network acts as the filtered image to be broadcast to viewers. Figure 2 illustrates the filtering and reconstruction achieved by the PECAM network. One disadvantage of the PECAM network is that the network could cause privacy leakage, as it might not work well when the privacy-sensitive objects are close to the camera.

Facial de-identification

Facial de-identification methods work by generating artificial faces and subsequently blending the generated faces into the original picture. While classical methods have used the k-same family of algorithms for the task, state-of-the-art methods rely on the generative power of generative adversarial networks (GANs) for this.

Sun et al. (2018), for example, use facial keypoints to condition adversarial autoencoders (deep convolutional GANs). The first stage of the proposed scheme uses as input either an obfuscated/redacted image or the original image. In the case where a blackhead or blurhead image is provided as input, a landmark generator which is adversarially trained generates estimates of facial landmarks as a facial landmark heatmap. Whereas when the original image is provided, a facial landmark detector extracts the landmark heatmap from the face present in the image. Stage 2 subsequently accepts as input the landmark heatmap concatenated with the blackhead original. Another adversarial DCGAN autoencoder accepts this as input and generates images into which realistic generated faces are inpainted. Results from this scheme can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Two-stage facial de-identification framework proposed by Sun et al. (2018)

Gafni et al. (2019) devise a live facial de-identification system. The method works by distancing the facial descriptors of a person in the image from a target image of the person provided. This target image can be any image of the person and need not be obtained from the same video stream. For this method, facial bounding boxes are initially obtained from the video frame, and keypoints are extracted from this setup. Using a similarity transformation to an averaged face, a transformation matrix is acquired from the keypoints. The face is then transformed using this transformation matrix. It is then passed through the network to obtain an output face along with a mask. An adversarial autoencoder network is devised for this task, through which the input image is re-created, along with an output mask that can be used to guide the network's output. The inverse of the similarity transformation is used to transform back this output face and the mask. After a linear per-pixel mixing of the input image and the output image weighted by the transformed mask, the result is merged into the original frame using the convex hull of facial keypoints, thereby obtaining the final generated facial output.

The approach by (Li and Lin, 2019) is especially interesting for the way it mixes both machine and perceptual obfuscation techniques. Based on the knowledge of both the facial attributes of persons observed and the distribution of those attributes in the real world (approximated by using the distribution of features in the dataset containing the image), this approach creates perceptually altered images. The model used aligns and crops faces using a deep alignment network, which uses a GoogleNet model and random forest models to perform facial feature extraction. This is then used as input to a custom privacy preserving attribute selection algorithm. This obfuscates the features of the face and lets the outputs of the model recreate the distribution of facial features present in the real world. Conditioned by the features selected by the algorithm in the previous step, a starGAN model (Choi et al., 2018) then generates a de-identified face. Finally, machine obfuscation methods are employed to protect the outputs from unauthorized machine learning models, adversarial perturbation, is used on the output image for this purpose, which in turn utilises the concept of a universal perturbation vector defined by the DeepFool algorithm (Moosavi-Dezfooli et al., 2016).

Total body abstraction

Total body abstraction methods aim to impart privacy by substituting the entire body of the subject being observed with a generated one in a perceptually pleasing manner. State-of-the-art methods in this category make use of semantic segmentation to segment out humans from frames. These then subsequently replace the subjects in the frames with visual abstractions such as avatars. Other popular abstractions include silhouettes, where the human is replaced by a binary mask of the person (and sometimes modified for various purposes) thereby removing textural information, and invisibility, where inpainting techniques replace the person in the visual with the environment / background thereby making the subject invisible in the frame.

The approach by Brkic et al. (2017) provides a particularly interesting visual abstraction method. This method relies on the use of generative adversarial models to generate full-body replacements. The method uses deep conditional GANs (DCGANs) to synthesize entire bodies of subjects. In this scheme, faces are generated using deep convolutional GAN models. The DCGAN used is trained on pairs of segmentation masks and images and is also trained to operate on masks with various levels of detail ranging from simple silhouette blobs to full-body segmentations with detailed tags for individual garments.

Substituting humans in visuals by avatars can also work to impart visual privacy (see Figure 3 left). These mostly build on the SMPL (skinned multi-person linear) model (Loper et al., 2015). One recent example is Frankmocap (Rong et al., 2020). This is built to be capable of both hand and body capture and replacement in real time. Since hands are small, they are harder to motion capture than most parts of the body. To solve this, the authors build a 3D monocular hand capture method that explicitly uses the hand part of the SMPL model. One drawback of this scheme is that garments are not modelled for the avatar. Research has recently also focused on improving the quality of the avatar in question. One such recent model is SMPLicit (Corona et al., 2021). This approach specifically allows the modelling of garments by using a semantically interpretable latent vector in the pipeline.

Gait anonymization

Gait is another important biomarker that can be used to identify persons as it is individually unique (Wang et al., 2003; Bashir et al., 2010; Liu and Sarkar, 2006; Zhang et al., 2004; Makihara et al., 2006; Bobick and Johnson, 2001). (Wan et al., 2018) provide a deeper treatment of the subject of gait recognition, and it is an active area of research. Gait anonymization is, however, a relatively newer and arguably under-explored direction. Typical video feed anonymization tools use filters such as pixelation and blurring assuming that the gait will be anonymized in the process (Agrawal and Narayanan, 2011). These approaches typically leave much to be desired, with the resulting video looking unnatural and thus easily detectable as filtered.

(Tieu et al., 2017) propose the use of deep neural networks for generating an anonymizing gait. This is generated by utilizing the original gait from frames of the visual feed, along with a custom 'noise gait' as inputs to a convolutional neural network. The network then outputs an anonymizing contour vector

for the model which, after processing, produces the anonymized gait, which is subsequently blended into the original scene.

Newer literature has focussed on leveraging the power of generative adversarial networks to generate the anonymized gaits. (Tieu et al., 2019b) create spatio-temporal generative models that can create perceptually natural gait sequences. The architecture of the model uses one generator and two discriminators. The generator accepts as input the original gait and a random noise to generate anonymized gaits. The first discriminator is a spatial discriminator which tries to distinguish the shape of real gaits from generated gaits at each frame. This accepts a contour vector extracted from frames of the gait as input. This is used to improve the shape of the generated gait, to make it seem more natural. The second discriminator is a temporal discriminator, created to learn to distinguish between the temporal continuity of the real gait and a generated gait. This discriminator determines whether the generated gait moves smoothly across frames. A contour sequence is subsequently fed through a long short-term memory network (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997), the outputs of nodes of which are concatenated, forming one vector used as input for the network. The generation process generates a binary anonymized gait, which is then colourized and merged into the original background. This process is known to work only on input silhouettes of high-quality and fails on low-quality silhouettes. As a follow-up to this work, (Tieu et al., 2019a) create a colourization network, in addition to a different STGAN based GAN architecture. Through this approach, the authors also provide gait anonymization for low-quality silhouettes.

3.2.2 Machine obfuscation

Those methods that aim to protect the privacy of users from unauthorized machine learning algorithms are classified under the umbrella of machine obfuscation techniques. The objective of machine obfuscation is to alter images in ways that cause misclassification in machine learning models used in tasks such as person or activity recognition. These alterations are also devised to be imperceptible to the human eye, to prevent humans from detecting the changes performed on the visual and to be perceptually natural enough for sharing on popular online photo sharing websites. Commonly known as attacks, state-of-the-art machine obfuscation methods utilize generative adversarial networks (GANs) for this task. (Shan et al., 2020) further sub-categorize machine obfuscation attacks into two different types - *Poisoning attacks* and *Evasion attacks*.

Poisoning attacks

Poisoning attacks aim to disrupt the training of machine learning models through the crafting of targeted 'poisoned' images. After the introduction of poisoned images to a dataset of images, deep neural network models trained on the dataset behave in unexpected ways. Poisoning attacks can be further split into 'clean label' attacks and 'model corruption' attacks.

In **clean label attacks**, adversarial noise is specifically crafted so that models trained on the dataset learn to misclassify a specific target image (typically that of a person), or a set of images containing the person (Shafahi et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2019). This is done by creating adversarial noise to alter the feature

space that is used by machine learning models for recognition. During testing, after encountering an unaltered image, a model classifies the image incorrectly due to it seeing a different feature vector for the person than what was observed during training. Most clean label attacks work on achieving misclassification of a single pre-selected image, although exceptions exist (Shan et al., 2020).

The objective of **model corruption attacks** is to prevent unauthorized data collection and model training. Model corruption attacks distort the feature space of images in a way that upon using the dataset containing the altered images for training, it reduces the overall accuracy of the model (Shen et al., 2019). The downside of these types of attacks are that they are easily detectable because the attack would be reflected in the drop in the model's accuracy.

Evasion attacks

Evasion attacks aim to create images that are difficult for facial recognition systems to identify. State-of-the-art methods rely on the creation of adversarial examples using specially created accessories, which upon being worn increases the chances of the subject being misidentified. Prominent examples of this sort include wearables like a specially crafted pair of spectacles (Sharif et al., 2016), adversarial stickers (Komkov and Petiushko, 2021), or adversarial patches (Brown et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2020; Thys et al., 2019). The downside of evasion attacks is that the presence of these are obvious to a human observer. Shan et al. (2020) also classify techniques that use adversarial models to alter faces to avoid detection under evasion attacks, while in this survey, it is classified under perceptual obfuscation techniques as they perceptually alter the person's appearance.

3.3 Alignment with PbD levels

Section 2.4.1 introduced a methodological approach in which different levels are specified for a system to ensure privacy by design. The most basic of these is at the sensor level. Moving up in scope, the classification advocates privacy to be ensured at the model level, system level, user interface level and at the highest level, privacy at the user level. The connection between this high-level classification of levels of privacy by design and the taxonomy of visual privacy protection methods presented in Section 3 is shown in Figure 5.

Intervention methods align with privacy preservation at the sensor level, as they intervene during the data collection phase to protect privacy of users and environments. Under the classification scheme proposed in this review, *blind vision* techniques could be classified as providing model-level privacy. State-of-the-art techniques like homomorphic encryption allow for machine learning models to infer from the data in a private manner. Boulemtafes et al. (2020) provide a more in-depth treatment on the subject of privacy preserving deep learning. Techniques that provide privacy at the user interface level obfuscate sensitive data using different methods. Under the classification scheme put forward in this review, techniques under the category of *visual obfuscation* and *data hiding* can be categorized as adding to user interface-level privacy of a system.

Figure 5. Connecting privacy levels from Mihailidis and Colonna (2020) to the taxonomy of visual privacy protection methods

3.4 Future directions

As perceptual and machine obfuscation are two orthogonal directions of research, algorithms can also be built such that they perform both machine and perceptual obfuscation. The authors consider this a promising research direction. The creation of methods which can perform reversible image filtering transformations through secure pipelines is another promising direction for research. This is useful in the case when reversibility is required, such as for an arbiter such as a judge or a doctor to view unedited footage to obtain full information about the obfuscated visuals in question. The acceptability of reconstructed images from filtered ones through reversible transformation in a judicial setting is also unclear, as reconstruction is an imperfect process; there is always the possibility of information loss during reconstruction through state-of-the-art methods.

There is also the need to understand the effects of applying the methods presented in the survey from a social scientific and judicial perspective. There is also a clear need for studies to ascertain the level of acceptance of different privacy preservation methods among the monitored subjects. It is also unclear as to the extent of the acceptability of reversible transformations for the subjects being monitored.

4. Secure transmission and storage of video data

4.1. Introduction

Video and images have extensively been used in ambient assisted living (AAL) applications. The multimedia data obtained from AAL systems can contain various personal data such as health data, visual, and speech-visual characteristics of persons and their habits as well as visual characteristics of their environment. Therefore, protection of sensitive private data of AAL applications using images and video is a challenging task. Especially when simple end devices equipped with microcontrollers, wearables and smartphones are used, which are typically connected to the network via a wireless communication link, it is difficult to ensure a high level of security and privacy during the transmission of the data. Additionally, if the data is transmitted over several network domains and using different transmission technologies and protocols, and finally processed at a remote location and stored on a server in a data center, it becomes very difficult to implement and guarantee the highest level of protection over the entire transmission and storage system and for the whole lifetime of the data.

The rapid development of video technologies, increase in data rates and processing speeds, wide use of the Internet and cloud computing as well as highly efficient video compression methods have made video encryption even more challenging. The traditional ciphers such as the Data Encryption Standard (DES) and the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) are mostly optimized and applied for encrypting text and binary data. Due to the fact that video streams contain a huge amount of data that need to be processed and transmitted almost in real-time, the traditional approaches are not very well suited for multimedia data. The use of these methods causes a large overhead and requires significant processing resources, which are usually not provided by energy-efficient, low-performance end devices or are very expensive to realize. Consequently, an efficient and robust encryption of multimedia data containing video together with using efficient compression methods are important prerequisites in achieving secure and efficient video transmission and storage.

In general, compression and encryption of video data can be combined in different ways. For example, encryption can take place before, during or after the data compression. Hence, an efficient and robust multimedia encryption algorithm should, in addition to providing a high level of security, also be able to work together with various compression methods and satisfy the following two requirements: (1) reduced processing time and (2) low memory usage.

In this section, we will indicate the main requirements for secure transmission and storage of video data in AAL applications and review recent works on efficient and robust encryption as well as secure storage of sensitive private data in order to improve the security and privacy levels of video-based AAL applications.

Figure 6. Security issues (adapted from (Mahapatra et al., 2020))

4.2 Attacks on AAL systems

AAL applications rely on the IoT network architecture, which defines a simple skeleton for the network. This architecture is based on several architectural models defined by the ETSI (European Telecommunication Standard Institute) and the ITU (International Telecommunication Union). In particular, according to (Mahapatra et al., 2020), the security architecture of an IoT system can be divided into three layers: (i) the perception layer, (ii) the network layer, and (iii) the application layer, as shown in Figure 6. The perception layer involves the collection of information that is obtained through sensors and controllers. After that, this information collected from IoT objects is transmitted via the network layer. The main security issues related to the network layer are related to spoofing attacks, selective forwarding attacks, cloning attacks and eavesdropping attacks.

The network layer of an IoT system is responsible for transmitting the information through different network areas and technologies. For this purpose, network technologies such as cellular networks (3G, 4G and 5G), wired networks (xDSL, DOCSIS, FTTH), WiFi, Zigbee and Bluetooth can be used. The data from a large number of end devices is aggregated and forwarded via gateways and routers. Actually, gateways act as intermediate nodes which collect data from different IoT devices. The network layer interconnects end devices via the network, i.e. the Internet, to data centers or directly to the sides of care/service providers. Thus, transferring a large amount of data between different nodes can cause security issues. The examples of attacks that may take place in the network layer are: the man-in-the-

middle attack, the sniffing attack, the DoS/DDos attack, the hello flood attack, the wormhole attack, the Sybil attack, the sinkhole attack and the traffic analysis attack.

The application layer deals with different types of applications such as the health care applications, smart home applications or industry application. Video-based AAL applications deal with both health care and smart home technologies. This layer allocates resources and processes, screens and selects data to be visualized by the user or the care service provider. Different attacks can occur at the application layer depending on the type of data: multimedia data, i.e. audio, video or image, and non-multimedia data, i.e. password, text. The attacks related to multimedia data can be, for example, the deep fake video and facial manipulation. Examples of attacks related to non-multimedia data are buffer overflow, code injection, phishing attack and eavesdropping. A short description of the above mentioned attacks is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Description of attacks at the network and application layers.

Attack	Description
spoofing attack	A device, a program or a person identifies itself as another one by falsifying data.
packet forwarding attack	Here, a malicious device may drop information or packets selectively or randomly. The attacker may corrupt the packet loss rate.
cloning attack	A cloning attack refers to the copying of information of an user or device to a clone, which can then be used to replace the original information. Cloning attacks can use sniffing, eavesdropping, and other technologies.
eavesdropping attack	Eavesdropping focuses on capturing small packets from the network and searching for any type of information within it.
man-in-the-middle attack	A man-in-the-middle attack is a general term for any attack in which a communication between two devices or users is intercepted by an unauthorized party, which either eavesdrops or impersonates one of the parties, making it appear as if it would be a normal exchange of information.
sniffing attack	A malicious device (sniffer) captures network traffic but does not change the packet nor affect the network performance.
DoS/DDos attack	In a Denial of Service (DoS) attack, the attacker tries to disable a network node for some time or prevent it from functioning correctly.
hello flood attack	A malicious device overflows other devices with HELLO messages.

Attack	Description
wormhole attack	Two malicious devices create a low-latency tunnel between them to cheat other nodes into thinking that this is the best channel or path for communication.
Sybil attack	A malicious device has multiple identities within the network, i.e. it appears with different identifiers.
sinkhole attack	A malicious device captures entire traffic and drops data packets instead of forwarding them
traffic analysis attack	In a traffic analysis attack, the network traffic is captured and analyzed to learn something about the system.
buffer overflow attack	In this attack type, an attacker can try to feed a carefully crafted data or instruction into a program that will cause the program to overflow buffers or overwrite portions of memory.
code injection attack	Code Injection attacks is a general term describing an injection and execution of malicious code by an attacker.
phishing attack	Phishing is a type of attack often used to steal user data such as login credentials. The recipient is tricked into clicking a malicious link, which can lead to revealing of sensitive information or installation of malware.

4.3 Review of security approaches for AAL applications

In this Subsection, we present a review of recently presented approaches that deal with security, confidentiality and privacy issues in communication systems used for transmission and storage of video and image data originating from AAL applications. Even though general and widely available concepts and methods can also be used in AAL applications, there are some particular characteristics of video-based AAL systems, as already mentioned in the introductory part of this section, which have to be taken into consideration when developing and implementing an effective concept for protecting image and video data.

4.3.1 Authentication and access control

As an integral part of any AAL system, communication technologies and networks need to provide a high level of confidentiality, integrity, and availability in order to meet very high requirements on security and privacy of AAL applications. An authentication protocol makes sure that only authorized users can access the AAL services and data. Such a protocol has been proposed and analyzed in (He and Zeadally, 2015). In this correspondence, the authors discuss the architecture of a typical AAL system based on

wireless body area network (WBAN) technologies as specified in the IEEE 802.15 standard and describe the proposed protocol. The encryption protocol is based on elliptic curve cryptography and is able to support several security requirements set by AAL as well as to withstand a number of different types of attacks (He and Zeadally, 2015). To achieve the security goals and to avoid using the complex public key infrastructure as in the traditional public key cryptography (PKC), the proposed protocol relies on the identity-based PKC. In order to assess the performance of the protocol, the authors estimate the protocol's computational cost in terms of execution time to execute various operations of the proposed authentication process and compare the results with those of two other recent authentication protocols. The results show the superior efficiency of the proposed protocol. Additionally, the authors discuss the robustness of the authentication protocol against a number of attacks such as replay attacks, impersonation attacks, server-spoofing attacks, man-in-the-middle attacks and modification attacks.

In (Kujis et al., 2019), the authors address the access control to systems and data of AAL applications in order to preserve the privacy of users. The presented approach is based on an easy and extendable policy language and uses context information for enabling AAL applications to adapt their behavior to current conditions such as changes in the environment or in the level of emergency. In particular, the system uses proxy servers and application specific proxy services to monitor and control data flows in Open Services Gateway initiative (OSGi) based systems. The access control system is able to manage access rights based on policies, which can be achieved without modifications on the core platform or the service logic. The authors present results of preliminary system tests and emphasize the need for more exhaustive field tests and a more extensive evaluation of the system performance.

4.3.2 Cryptography

Establishment of a secure communication link between medical user devices and remote hosts or servers in an AAL system is an important step to ensure a secure access to the critical health data. However, the traditional security protocols, which typically make use of complex cryptographic algorithms, can hardly be entirely implemented and executed in constrained medical devices due to the limited resources available in such devices. The authors of the paper (Porambage et al., 2015) therefore propose a lightweight, proxy-based protocol for authentication and key establishment. The protocol can be used for an end-to-end secure connection initiation with highly resource constrained medical devices. Additionally, the authors show a large reduction in energy consumption at the sensor node side by at least a factor of 13 in comparison to the famous HIP-DEX and HIP-BEX protocols.

In (Anusha et al., 2020), the authors propose to use a carrier image as the cover file and the data is kept secure with the assistance of the symmetric key, which both the sender and the specified receiver or person must process. The proposed methodology performs better and shows an improvement in peak signal-to-noise-ratio (PSNR) and signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) values than the existing wavelet transform methodology as shown in experimental results. The proposed method is implemented using MATLAB.

4.3.3 Privacy

Privacy concerns of users of AAL applications and services must be addressed and mitigated. In a recent survey (Seliem et al., 2018), the authors review existing research and propose solutions to raise privacy concerns in the IoT environment from a multipoint view and to identify the risks and mitigations. The paper provides an evaluation of privacy issues in IoT System concerns due to resource constraints. The authors describe an IoT solution that embraces a variety of privacy concerns such as: identification, tracking, monitoring and profiling. Additionally, they discuss the mechanisms and architectures for protecting IoT data in case of mobility in different layers: device layer, infrastructure/platform layer, and application layer.

4.3.4 Security in device-to-device communication

Ensuring security and privacy preservation at the level of device-to-device (D2D) communication is an important task towards securing the entire AAL system. In a recent review paper (Haus et al., 2017), the authors present the state-of-the-art systems and solutions for improving security and privacy level in D2D communication, discuss challenges, requirements and characteristics of various recently proposed approaches as well as derive a set of recommendations by identifying and analyzing best practices. In particular, the authors address methods that concentrate on enhancing network communication, peer discovery, proximity services, and location privacy. Additionally, they consider a number of potential issues linked to diversity of interconnected devices, limitation of resources, legal concerns, user incentive, deployability of solutions, conflicts regarding different requirements, and the need for suitable metrics and evaluation tools to objectively analyze and compare different proposals against their security and privacy levels.

Secure transmission in AAL applications using an IoT network might be classified into five categories: block chain, cluster, location, trust and routing (Haus et al., 2017), as presented in Figure 7. These approaches can be used to improve the security level of data transmission in the network.

In the *cluster-based* scheme, the fuzzy approach is used to defend against attacks such as wormhole and hello flood attacks. This class of secure transmission technique uses algorithms based on fuzzy logic, gravitational search algorithms, ant colony algorithms and genetic algorithms.

The *location-based* approach focuses on the location and dynamic privacy protection to defend against internal attacks.

The *blockchain-based* approaches are based on a decentralized and distributed technology to tackle the privacy and security challenges within the IoT networks. These approaches include anonymization, encryption, differential privacy, private contract, and mixing (Hassan et al., 2019).

The *trust-based* methods involve trust management actions to develop a security policy, assign credentials to entities including the verification of the policy fulfillment, justify access rights, and

Figure 7. IoT secure transmission techniques

delegate trust to third parties. These methods can be used to prevent different attacks such as DoS attack and node replication.

Malicious devices can instigate a number of attacks to cause a serious degradation of network performance, disrupt data traffic and constrain network resources through exploiting vulnerabilities of underlying routing protocols. In order to detect such attacks, assess their vulnerability level, reduce the security risk and enhance the efficiency of the routing mechanisms various *routing-based* approaches can be applied (Muzammal et al. 2021). The routing-based approaches can be used to prevent DDoS attack, DoS attack, black hole, gray hole, and Sybil attacks. Apart from the security issues, energy efficiency problems in AAL applications based on IoT systems are an essential design concern. It is one of the significant features because IoT sensors are energy constrained. approaches have been proposed in the literature in the context of health care and smart home. For example, the work in (Wang et al., 2018) proposes a secure transmission scheme for transmitting the uplink data in IoT networks. In this work, multiple energy-constrained relays and energy-constrained sources harvest the energy from power beacons (PBs). Three relay selection schemes are considered for selection of the best PB (Wang et al., 2018). In (Chen et al., 2018), the authors propose a secure energy efficient transmission protocol for uplink data transmission in IoT, which uses a controller with multiple sensors. However, this approach is not efficient enough to boost the secure energy efficiency and secrecy outage probability.. In (Randhave et al., 2019), the authors propose an energy efficient cross layer approach for object security of constrained application protocols for IoT devices. This approach is based on the blockchain technique. According to (Mahapatra et al., 2020), using this approach can lead to energy savings by a factor of 10 and a further reduction in the memory footprint.

Another important goal of AAL applications based on IoT transmission systems is to ensure trust and security in data sharing. Several works proposed in the literature have developed methods to overcome some attacks that may occur in the system and in different types of application. In (Casola et al., 2019), the authors propose the use of the Montimage Monitoring Tools (MMT) for monitoring the threats and

defending against the attacks, in the context of the healthcare system. In this approach, a data filtering process was used to collect information from diverse sources. This approach is, however, not very efficient in protecting data against unauthorized access.

Finally, the security level of AAL applications that use IoT technologies can largely be affected by cyberattacks. In fact, the cyber attack can be considered as one of the most important attacks on an IoT system. The main targets of such an attack are the health care system, media and web sites. The most known cyber attacks are: DoS, DDoS, attack on privacy, attacking passwords and phishing.

In (Alshehri et al., 2019) the authors propose a widespread trust management fuzzy logic based approach. This approach is very effective in identifying malicious nodes in the network. However, this proposal has a convergence issue, which occurs between the average trust value and actual trust value. Table 3 presents an overview of the above discussed techniques and approaches .

Table 3. Security in device to device (D2D) communication

Technique	Application	Objective	Network technology	Layer	Attack	Reference
Trust based	Smart home	Provide uplink transmission with security	LTE, IEEE802.15.4	Perception layer	Eavesdropping attack from unauthorized devices	(Wang et al., 2018)
Cluster based	Health care	Provide uplink transmission with energy efficiency	Wireless sensor network, Bluetooth	Network layer	Passive eavesdropping	(Chen et al., 2018)
Cluster based	Smart home	Reduce IoT threats	Wireless sensor network, IEEE802.15	Application layer	Cyber attack	(Randhave et al., 2019)
Trust based	Health care	Tackle security issues in IoT	Wireless network, 6LoWPAN	Application layer	Distributed DoS (DDoS) attack	(Casola et al., 2019)

Technique	Application	Objective	Network technology	Layer	Attack	Reference
Routing based	Smart home	Detect attacks and provide security	Wireless sensor network, IEEE 802.15.4	Network layer	Routing attacks, Rank and Sybil attacks	(Alshehri et al., 2019)

4.3.5 Surveys, projects and use Cases

This section presents some examples of recent projects, surveys and use cases related to security and privacy of data transmission and storage in IoT and AAL systems.

Streaming the video content over IoT networks set completely different requirements on the network infrastructure as, for example, asynchronously transmitting text or small data packets originating from simple sensor nodes. In (Hamoudy et al., 2017), the authors present an overview of different video streaming techniques with a particular focus on the security of video in IoT. They give a comprehensive overview of security issues and challenges in video streaming in IoT. In particular, the authors consider and discuss main elements needed to achieve a certain information security level for IoT applications regarding multimedia connection, computation, and service and according to the security strategy, required performance and video streaming security. These elements include an appropriate key management, watermarking and encryption. However, due to the limitation in processing power and energy consumption of end devices, a complex and secure encryption of the video content is difficult. For this reason, selective encryption techniques gained interest for such applications. Selective encryption approaches can make possible large savings in the computational effort by about 95% (Almasalha et al., 2014), but at the same time perceive a certain loss of security robustness.

In (Tawalbeh et al., 2020), the authors discuss the background of IoT systems and security measures. They identify different security and privacy issues and various approaches that can be used to secure the IoT components. The authors also present existing security solutions and discuss the privacy models best suitable for different IoT layers. The main contribution of this work is the proposal for a new IoT layered model. The proposed model is implemented through three layers, namely a lower layer, a middle layer and a top layer. Each one of these layers uses, respectively, the Amazon Web Service (AWS) as a virtual machine, a Raspberry Pi 4 kit, and a cloud enabled IoT environment in AWS. The authors apply security certificates to improve the security level of data transfer between layers as well as secure protocols and session's management to ensure the privacy of the user's information and to eliminate possible security vulnerabilities.

An overview of privacy and security challenges in the area of smart home applications is presented in the paper (Bugeja et al., 2016). These challenges are related to: (1) devices, which are usually resource

constrained, headless nature, and integrated in a tamper resistant package, (2) communication, especially regarding heterogeneous protocols and dynamics characteristics; and (3) service issues related to longevity expectation. The authors present security and privacy approaches related to each challenge and discuss the prominent areas where further investigation is required to ensure privacy and security in smart connected homes.

Security and privacy issues related to the use of smart home personal assistant (SPA) devices must also be considered. The most important attacks and possible countermeasures are categorized in (Edu et al., 2021). The authors of this paper have found that even though the attack surface is vast and there exist a significant number of research articles related to the security of SPA systems, the most of the current research concentrates on issues related to the interaction between the user and the smart home personal assistants. Only a little research effort is considering the complexity of the entire system. The authors propose to consider in further works an improvement of the authentication and authorization models and mechanisms as well as to build secure and privacy-aware speech recognition, develop AI-based security and privacy countermeasures, consider further profiling attacks and defenses and to further improve user awareness and usability.

A particular attention should be paid to children in healthcare settings. For example, iWithin the DESEOS research project (Antón et al., 2020), novel devices and applications are developed to enhance the life and wellbeing of children in healthcare settings, both during the hospitalization period and the post hospitalization. The project applies the ambient assisting living (AAL) paradigm to increase the quality of life of children in treatment. In order to reduce problems related to long hospitalization periods, the authors propose different scenarios in different daily environments, i.e., in the classroom and the hospital room. This project targets two different aspects: (1) a comprehensive integration of security elements into an AAL system, to ensure a high level of security and privacy, and (2) an appropriate system design allowing it to react to changes in the context and scalable enough to handle communication between a large number of users.

4.3.6 Discussion and outlook

The data generated from AAL applications, for example video, images or any data originating from various sensor nodes travels from home networks over the Internet to cloud providers, where it resides for the rest of its life. Assuring security of these data during transmission over the Internet and furthermore ensuring privacy for the entire life period of this data remains a challenge. The above listed solutions have been typically adopted using traditional encryption algorithms, which are not designed to encrypt streaming video and audio data. Furthermore, protecting AAL applications from unauthorized access and manipulation increases the work to be done. Adding the rich hardware landscape of existing devices (PCs, tablets, smartphones, etc.) further increases the chance to compromise AAL applications. Image and face manipulation, especially using AI algorithms, are the main threats now. Usage of several AI algorithms for video manipulation – a so-called deep fake video - creates an even bigger threat for violating AAL application security and privacy.

Security and privacy in AAL applications is a mandatory feature and it should be treated in every segment: from data transmission to storage. Existing algorithms and protocols must be extended to deliver more efficiency in computing and storage resources. In Table 4, we summarize different approaches for improving the security of data transmission and storage. The characteristics of these approaches regarding their characteristics such as the achievable level of security, privacy and anonymity, the intended AAL application, and attack resistance are shown in Table 5, while the methods used to secure data transmission and storage can be seen in Table 6.

Table 4. Considered and reviewed approaches

Approach	Short Description
Access and policy control in OSGi environments	A system based on Open Services Gateway initiative (OSGi) software platform and proxy services to monitor and control data flows on the service level. An access control system is used to manage access rights based on rules. The rules can be defined by a policy language and context information for various AAL use cases.
Authentication based on elliptic curve cryptography	The proposed protocol for WBAN-based AAL systems is based on elliptic curve cryptography and is able to support several security requirements set by AAL as well as to withstand a number of different types of attacks.
Privacy preservation in IoT environments	Presents significant challenges on IOT devices and scenarios related to privacy (identifying, tracking, monitoring, profiling).
Cryptography and steganography	Image steganography technique used to hide audio signal in images in the transform domain using wavelet transform or with white Gaussian noise.
Security in IoT and smart connected homes	Identify constraints, evaluate solutions and discuss a number of solutions with regard to different levels: device, service, communication; Classification of technologies and protocols; IoT layered model.
Authentication, secure data transmission and digital certificates	An AAL based project to improve the quality of life of hospitalised children during hospitalisation and after hospitalisation as treated within the DESEOS project. It uses access control mechanisms and TLS/SSL and HTTPS protocols.

Table 5. Overview of the approaches and their main characteristics regarding security, privacy and anonymity levels as well as AAL applications and resistance to attack types.

Approach	Security, Privacy and Anonymity	Type of AAL Application	Attack Resistance	Reference
Access and policy control in OSGi environments	Policy / privacy / OSGi security extensions	Various AAL applications and use cases	n/a	(Kujis et al., 2019)
Authentication based on elliptic curve cryptography	High security and privacy levels	AAL applications and systems using WBAN technologies	Resistant to replay attacks, impersonation attacks, server-spoofing attacks, man-in-the-middle attacks and modification attacks	(He et al., 2015)
Privacy preservation in IoT environments	yes - discussion about different existing work: (blurring , alter specific part of the image, masking personal information before sharing, using K-anonymity algorithm	Medical AAL application to monitor personal health	DDoS attacks and man in the middle	(Seliem et al., 2018)
Cryptography and steganography	High privacy level	Various AAL applications	Gaussian noise - not tested on histogram, cripint etc.	(Hamnoudi et al., 2017) and (Dutta et al., 2017)
Smart connected Home	Security and privacy at the device, communication, and service levels	Smart connected homes, mobile health service, health care (chronic disease), <i>people</i> with disabilities	n/a	(Bugeja et al., 2016) and (Tawalbeh et al., 2020)

Approach	Security, Privacy and Anonymity	Type of AAL Application	Attack Resistance	Reference
Authentication, secure data transmission and digital certificates	Security at the communication level	health care of hospitalised children	n/a	(Antón et al., 2012)

Table 6. Overview of the approaches and their main characteristics regarding communication technology and methods for authentication, data encryption and secure communication and storage

Approach	Communication technology / protocol	Authentication and authorization method	Data encryption methods	Local / external / distributed storage	Secure communication / secure storage	Reference
Access and policy control in OSGi environments	OSGi / proxy services / XML / HTTP Gateway / XACML	n/a	n/a	External storage	n/a	(Kujis et al., 2019)
Authentication based on elliptic curve cryptography	WBAN (IEEE 802.15)	Mutual authentication	Identity-based public key cryptography (PKC), Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), Hash Message Authentication Code (HMAC)	n/a	Secure communication, Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) protocol	(He et al., 2015)
Privacy preservation in IoT environments	IEEE 802.15.4 ; RFID, IEEE 802.15.4e	User identification, face recognition, fingerprint, voice recognition, utility monitoring and controlling	Algorithm based on xor operation, Pauth key protocol, keying mechanisms	External / local	Secure channel using Ipsec, end to end authentication and key agreement, security routing , network virtualisation , using IPv6	(Seliem et al., 2018)

Approach	Communication technology / protocol	Authentication and authorization method	Data encryption methods	Local / external / distributed storage	Secure communication / secure storage	Reference
Cryptography and steganography	HTTP	n/a	XOR	n/a	n/a	(Hamnoudi et al., 2017) and (Dutta et al., 2017)
Smart connected Home	IEEE 802.15.4 ; IEEE 802.15.4 ; 6LoWPAN	Each device needs a policy, then it can perform connect, receive, publish, or subscribe; firewall, IDS, IPS	Certificates, private keys, K-anonymity, cryptographic scheme; attribute based encryption	n/a	MQTT Protoc, VPN	(Bugeja et al., 2016) and (Tawalbeh et al., 2020)
Authentication, secure data transmission and digital certificates	Various wireless and wired communication technologies	SOAP-based Web service APIs	X.509 V3 Certificate	External Storage	TLS /SSL; Open SSL; XMPP; HTTPs	(Antón et al., 2012)

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